

Healing Communities

What if we *collectively* had the capacity
to *overcome* any crisis in a matter of *days*?

A method for *teams of teams* to:

- *listen* to each other,
 - *agree* on priorities,
 - put in *commons* resources,
 - create *few* but essential and freely adaptable solutions.
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Ever since I was young, I have sought to find how to contribute meaningfully to the community, while being fully myself. Called to different interests than my peers, I began to explore the mysteries of group dynamics. Many cycles of study and practice led me to an awareness: suffering, misery (physical and spiritual), violence, are often generated by stories we learn as children, and pass on through generations.

I became convinced that, **within months**, we could ensure that all people could live decently and in harmony, if we dared to listen – literally and symbolically – to our Heart, to the Other's. We would commit ourselves to a path that celebrates our Humanity, connects us to Nature within and beyond, and nourishes our Souls.

Indeed, tackling complex, wicked challenges requires abandoning the logic of a machine-body, the illusion of technical solutions built without personal commitment, so that we can raise our collective, human consciousness. This means providing ways for the whole population to listen to their different realities, and to quickly reach a popular consensus on how to overcome these challenges in ways that strengthen solidarity.

According to the creator of Captcha tests,¹ one million people could translate Wikipedia into a new language in 80 hours. Let us imagine what such a group could achieve if they had the capacity to sincerely agree on essential common projects, and implement them in a matter of days – free/libre and open source knowledge and infrastructures that could easily be adopted, reproduced and enriched across territories?

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This five-part thesis documents six years of intense creation and research that enabled me to design how such a process could unfold.

First, I present my journey to the PhD, and how my research took shape through cycles of prototyping. I introduce the idea of the commons, which is to understand that people – not corporations or the state – have all the resources needed to overcome the challenges we face. This builds on the oeuvre of Elinor Ostrom,² who showed that ordinary people can self-organise efficiently to preserve resources, and Stefano Rodotà,³ who pledged that any resource that meets basic needs must be managed in a participatory way, regardless of who owns it.

Secondly, I talk about Breathing Games,⁴ a commons I co-founded to make respiratory health fun. I show how this initiative, which initially objectified the children concerned – by thinking their health in their place –, then opened up a space for young people to share their subjective experience in a playful way that was beneficial to their peers. I share how an ethic and aesthetic of commoning enabled us to engage over 450 volunteers, and mutualise resources from Canada, Switzerland, France, Italy, and South Korea.

Thirdly, I propose four levers to build solidarity-driven ecosystems. We need to:

- bring diverse people together for ludic events to overcome loneliness. For example, the online hackathons that mobilised 150,000 people at the start of the crown-crisis.⁵
- generate collective value to overcome material limitations. For example, the autonomous networks of makers, who shared designs and manufactured over 48 million medical supplies while industry was at a standstill.⁶
- facilitate agreements across teams of teams to overcome power games. For example, the Emerging Change, developed in Quebec schools and Swiss multinationals, which enables teams to thrive and excel by establishing a ritual dialogue between the whole team and its leader, thus avoiding competition between individuals.⁷
- revisit collective narratives to break free from self-servitude. For example, challenging the belief that an authority – parent, teacher, employer, politician, caregiver – can take care of our needs better than we can.⁸

Fourthly, I present the Geneva festival 'taking care together',⁹ a nine-day event created in 122 days thanks to 115 co-hosts. I quantify the collective value created by the Breathing Games and the festival at 2.2 million Swiss francs, 4/5 of which was generated by volunteer contributions.

Next, I provide a step-by-step facilitation method that could help thousands of people coordinate their efforts around a limited number of modular projects. I then outline how this model could re-create education, outdate systemic corruption, resurrect democracy, and heal our dis-ease when we over-invest in the mind.

Finally, I summarise what I have learnt, and list about 600 references that inspired me. This creation-as-research¹⁰ can be freely reproduced and enriched (Creative Commons BY-SA licence, editable LaTeX format).

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References

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11. *Concordia Salus*, which means *Salvation through a state of peaceful agreement*, is the motto of Concordia University, and of the city of Tio'tia:ke / Montreal.